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Acronyms and abbreviations

%-wt	mass percentage	ICP-OES	Inductively Coupled Plasma - Optical Emission Spectroscopy
BET	Brunauer-Emmett-Teller Analysis	IR	Infrared
CHS	Carbon / Hydrogen / Sulphur Analyzer	LHV	Lower Heating Value (Calorific Value)
CHSNO	Carbon / Hydrogen / Sulphur / Nitrogen / Oxygen Analyzer	MMX	Miscanthus Mix
CRW	Critical Raw Material	SDD	Silicon Drift Detector
CW	Clean Wood	SGR	Switchgrass
DW	Demolition Wood	TCD	Thermal Conductivity Detector
EDXRF	Energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence	TGA	Thermogravimetric analysis
FC	Fixed Carbon	VM	Volatile Matter
ICP	Inductively Coupled Plasma	XRD	X-ray diffraction
		XRF	X-ray fluorescence

Acronyms used to identify consortium members

EUCORE	EU CORE Consulting s.r.l
RIC	Centrum Badan i Innowacji Pro-Akademia Stowarzyszenie

1. Publishable executive summary

This report presents the results of the analyses of five types of biomass selected for further research work in the BeBOP project, namely the recovery of valuable elements (WP7, *Enabling technologies at lab-scale for SOEC characterisation and resource recovery*, T7.2, *Recovery elements from solid gasification residues via leaching*, WP8, Technology validation: SOEC and gasification residues recovery - T8.2, Leaching conditions validation and T8.3, Assessment of the recovery of elements via innovative combinations of physio-chemical processes) and the pilot-scale tests of the entire gasification and bio/e-methanol synthesis chain in WP3, TRL6 testing of the integrated Biomass to MeOH system.

The investigated biomass types were:

- Clean, commercial grade wood pellets;
- Post-consumer, demolition wood chips;
- Miscanthus pellets, a blend of Miscanthus x Giganteus and seed-based hybrids, both grown on contaminated, post-industrial marginal land in Southern Poland;
- Hay pellets, commercial grade;
- Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum*), grown on post-industrial marginal land in Greece.

The analyses performed on the samples of the abovementioned biomass types involved proximate (moisture content, ash content, volatile matter and fixed carbon) analysis as well as ultimate (elemental) analysis. The latter one included both the main constituents (carbon, hydrogen, sulphur, nitrogen and oxygen) and the inorganic (trace) elements.

Besides the biomass samples, also char samples were analysed for their composition, using the same techniques described above, extended by the XRD (crystalline structures) and BET (surface area) analyses, which were performed to get the information relevant from the leaching and recovery task point of view.

Char samples were obtained by pyrolyzing the raw biomass in a bench-scale, batch pyrolysis/gasification setup, by exposing batches of biomass to an inert atmosphere at the temperature of max. 550°C, until complete devolatilization. Such pyrolysis conditions allowed to preserve the maximum of the inorganic ash constituents in the char, which is relevant for the activities related to the recovery of elements via leaching.

The results obtained from the analyses described above in general were in agreement with the expected parameters of woody and herbaceous biomass, as found in the literature. Due to the high importance of the elemental composition of the inorganic fraction of the char samples, an additional focus was put on this aspect. Here, different results were obtained for the same sample if analysed at a different laboratory, but using the same technique (ICP-OES), and the differences sometimes reach up even to an order of the magnitude. It was concluded that these differences were caused by the different digestion methods applied by different analytical laboratories, as some of them were using microwave-assisted digestion in nitric acid and some digestion in *aqua regia*. Despite the provided information about the nature of the sample to be analysed, not all laboratories applied the most aggressive digestion method (nitric acid and microwaves), as suggested, e.g., by the US EPA method 3052. It has to be stressed, that the deviations among the samples were not caused by the inhomogeneous nature of the substrate, as the samples analysed *in duplo* yielded the results which differed significantly less than the analytical results of the same material delivered by different laboratories. Therefore, it is advisable to impose the digestion method to be applied when having the samples analysed by external laboratories.

2. Introduction

Biomass is the feedstock for the BeBOP solution, where ultimately it will be converted from a solid energy carrier with varying chemical composition (especially the moisture content, ash content and ash composition) and appearance (pellets, chips, briquettes, bales, etc.) into a liquid energy carrier with constant and known properties: methanol. As the biomass is one of the process input streams at the beginning of the process chain, its properties will affect multiple units of operation, mainly the gasifier and the gas cleaning unit. Therefore, it is crucial to quantify the properties of the selected types of biomass and to assess their influence on the operation of the feeding system, the gasifier and the gas cleaning unit.

In addition, as the BeBOP solution aims to close the loop and maximize the use of the resources, an investigation of the recovery of valuable elements from the solid gasification residues (char, ash) is planned. In order to assess both the recovery potential and the recovery efficiency, the chemical composition of the char, and especially of its inorganic part (ash) is necessary.

This report presents the results of the analyses of four types of biomass selected for further research work in the BeBOP project, namely the recovery of valuable elements (WP7, *Enabling technologies at lab-scale for SOEC characterisation and resource recovery*, T7.2, *Recovery elements from solid gasification residues via leaching*, WP8, *Technology validation: SOEC and gasification residues recovery* - T8.2, *Leaching conditions validation* and T8.3, *Assessment of the recovery of elements via innovative combinations of physio-chemical processes*) and the pilot-scale tests of the entire gasification and methanol synthesis chain in WP3, *TRL6 testing of the integrated Biomass to MeOH system*. Next to the biomass characterization results, also the results of the characterization of chars originating from these biomasses are provided.

3. Biomass selection and supply

Already during the proposal design phase, five different types of biomass were pre-selected. Clean wood was chosen as the basic (reference) fuel. Due to its low ash content, uniform appearance (graded pellets, chips or briquettes) and commercial availability it is an excellent baseline feedstock, which will also cause minimal problems during the operation of the gasifier and, by giving stable product gas parameters, it allows to focus on other, more demanding process aspects, such as gas upgrading, SOEC integration or methanol synthesis.

On the long term, during the industrial deployment of the BeBOP methanol synthesis (but also other processes that use biomass as a feedstock), clean wood is not the most sustainable fuel. Therefore, based on the biomass sustainability and circularity, four additional alternative types of biomass were pre-selected:

- Miscanthus grown on polluted soils - phytoremediation;
- Recovery of post-consumer wood;
- Willow or poplar (also from phytoremediation sites);
- Straw pellets.

Apart from the clean wood (pellets), which are commercially available throughout Europe, other types of biomass were planned to be acquired from smaller, local plantations or other research projects dealing with biomass cultivation or phytoremediation. This, however turned out to be an issue, especially for willow and poplar. However, the aspect of the cultivation of biomass on polluted soils was very important, as otherwise this type of fuel would not significantly differ from the clean wood pellets in terms of ash composition, and while very relevant as a sustainable source of biomass it would be much less relevant from the recovery of elements study point of view. Former European research projects dealing with phytoremediation were contacted:

- [AGRONICKEL](#) (Facce Surplus 1st call);
- [GOLD](#) (Horizon 2020, GA 101006873);
- [Phy2SUDOE](#) (V Interreg South West Europe, SOE4/P5/E1021).

Ultimately, it was agreed with the coordinator of the GOLD project (CRES, Greece) to deliver Switchgrass (*Panicum Virgatum*), cultivated on one of the remediation sites operated by the institute. Table 1 shows an overview of the biomass types ultimately selected for further analysis and use in the project. The processing of biomass and their analyses are described in the next sections.

Table 1. An overview of the biomass types finally selected for further analysis and use in the project.

Biomass type / name	Abbreviation	Appearance	Producer / supplier	Short description
Clean wood	CW	Pellets, 6 mm	Barlinek S.A. (PL)	Commercial, A1-grade wood pellets
Recovery / post-consumer/ demolition wood	DW	Chips	Own collection and processing at RIC	Painted and impregnated wooden fence boards, pieces of OSB and other scrap wood
Miscanthus Mix	MMX	Pellets, 6 mm	IETU (PL)	A 50/50 blend of M. x Giganteus and seed-based hybrid genotypes cultivated at a post-industrial site in Upper Silesia region (Poland)
Hay	HAY	Pellets, 15 mm	Höveler (DE)	Commercial feed-grade hay pellets
Switchgrass	SGR	Chaff	CRES (GR)	Energy crop cultivated on polluted, marginal land

4. Biomass bench-scale pyrolysis/gasification setup and procedure

4.1 Bench-scale batch pyrolysis/gasification setup design

To produce the char from the selected raw biomass, a laboratory pyrolysis/gasification station was constructed. Figure 1 shows a diagram of the setup, consisting of a pyrolysis vessel placed in a special furnace constructed in-house (Figure 3), which was mounted on a scale (KERN EOC 60K-3) to monitor the mass loss, and thus control the pyrolysis/gasification process phases. An inert gas (Nitrogen) was fed into the vessel using a mass flow controller (Bronkhorst High-Tech F-201CB), on one hand to flush the vessel before the process and also to expel the produced gases from the vessel. The pyrolysis/gasification gases were directed to a set of impingers, in which the condensable gasification/pyrolysis products were trapped. The impingers were cooled in an in-house made cooling vessel connected to a cooling bath circulator (WITEG WCR-12). The purified gas was routed to a flare to combust the remaining volatile organic compounds. Figure 2 shows the picture of the laboratory pyrolysis/gasification station.

Figure 1. Bench-scale batch pyrolysis/gasification setup diagram.

Figure 2. Photo of the bench-scale batch pyrolysis/gasification stand.

Figure 3. In-house constructed customized furnace.

The uniformity of the char preparation conditions for each biomass was ensured by the use of an in-house-developed process control application (Figure 4) integrated with the following devices: a scale (KERN EOC 60K-3), a mass flow controller (Bronkhorst High-Tech F-201CB) and a furnace temperature controller (SIMEX PUR-44D). The application also includes a temperature chart and a mass loss chart based on which the process was controlled.

Figure 4. A screenshot of the application for pyrolysis/gasification process control.

4.2 Experimental procedure

To ensure repeatability of the pyrolysis process when working with different types of biomass, the process had to be divided into phases. The duration of the exposure of the biomass to the elevated temperature inside the vessel and its effects on the mass loss were carefully monitored. The first phase of the process was the drying of the biomass. As each biomass had a different initial moisture content, the drying time also varied and was controlled depending on the observed mass loss. An example of the mass loss progress in time is shown in Figure 5 below. During this process, the temperature in the vessel was gradually increased to 120°C and the mass change and the condensation of water vapor in the impingers were observed. Once the mass curve had flattened, the second phase (biomass devolatilization) began. The temperature was gradually increased to 400°C. Each biomass type required a unique approach, as the volatilization processes began at a different temperature and exhibited varying intensities. Again, thanks to real-time mass measurement, the process was controlled by the slope of the mass loss curve. After reaching a temperature of approximately 400°C and flattening the mass loss curve, the final phase of char preparation was initiated: carbonization at 550°C. This temperature was maintained for an hour, then the heating was turned off and the system was allowed to cool while continuously purging with nitrogen to avoid the oxidation of the hot char by the air that otherwise could diffuse into the vessel from the surroundings.

Figure 5. A screenshot of the mass loss graph.

4.3 Experimental results

In preparation for further research, in total 6 kg of char were produced, approximately 1.5 kg from each biomass, i.e. MMX, CW, DW, HAY and SGR. The initial mass of raw biomass needed to produce 1.5 kg of char varied between 4 and 6 kg, and depended on the ash content of the biomass. Figure 6 through Figure 13 to follow show each biomass type before and after the pyrolysis process. In order to produce these amounts of char, the pyrolysis process had to be repeated multiple times. The produced char was then stored in gas-tight bins for further research work.

Figure 6. MMX pellets before pyrolysis.

Figure 7. MMX pellets after pyrolysis.

Figure 8. CW pellets before pyrolysis.

Figure 9. CW pellets after pyrolysis.

Figure 10. HAY pellets before pyrolysis.

Figure 11. HAY pellets after pyrolysis.

Figure 12. DW before pyrolysis.

Figure 13. DW after pyrolysis.

Figure 14. SGR before pyrolysis.

Figure 15. SGR after pyrolysis.

5. Biomass, char and ash characterization

5.1 Analytical methods

The characterization of biomass and its conversion products requires the use of a set of complementary analytical techniques that provide insight into their chemical composition, thermal behaviour, and structural features. Accurate determination of these parameters is essential to evaluate the suitability of biomass as a renewable energy source, to optimize thermochemical conversion processes, and to assess the composition of resulting residues such as char and ash [1] [2].

In this study a combination of elemental, thermal, spectroscopic and structural analyses was applied (see Table 2) to provide a comprehensive characterization of the selected biomass samples. The analytical techniques employed include elemental analysers (Carbon / Hydrogen / Sulphur -CHS- and Carbon / Hydrogen / Sulphur / Nitrogen / Oxygen -CHNSO), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), bomb calorimetry, X-ray fluorescence (XRF), X-ray diffraction (XRD), inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES), and Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) surface area analysis. These complementary methods enable the quantification of major elements, determination of energy content, and identification of inorganic phases and mineral transformations. Initially, also Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) and Scanning Electron Microscopy-Energy Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDX) were planned to apply to the char samples. However, due to the complex matrix, dominated by the carbonaceous structures and difficulties in the reproducibility of the analytical results at micro scale as will be shown in Sections 5.2 and 5.3, these analyses were not performed during the work described in this report. Nonetheless, the option to apply them to specific samples during the project implementation is still open.

Table 2. Analytical methods applied for the most relevant characterizations of the selected types of biomass from the point of view of the research work planned in the BeBOP project.

Analytical Method	Main Parameters	Relevant Standards / Literature
TGA	Proximate analysis: Moisture, Ash, Volatile matter, Fixed carbon content	PN-EN UNI EN ISO 18134-3:2023 - Solid biofuels - Determination of moisture content PN-EN ISO 18122:2023-05 - Solid biofuels - Determination of ash content
Elemental Analysis (CHS/CHNSO)	Content of the major elements: C, H, N, S, O	PN-EN EN ISO 16994:2016-10 - Solid biofuels - Determination of total content of sulphur and chlorine
Bomb Calorimetry	Gross Calorific Value, Net Calorific Value	PN-EN ISO 18125:2017 - Solid biofuels - Determination of calorific value
ICP-OES	Trace elements, quantitative analysis: Si, Al, K, Ca, P, Mg, Fe, Ti, Na, Zn, S, Li, Sr, Mn, Ba, B, Pb, As, Cd, Cr, Ni, Zr, Co, Se, Bi, Cu, Mo, Hg, Sb, Sn, V	PN-EN UNI EN ISO 11885:2009 - Determination of selected elements by inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES)
XRD	Crystalline structure, Phase composition, Mineralogical identification	ISO/TS 23361:2024 Nanotechnologies - Crystallinity of cellulose nanomaterials by powder X-ray diffraction (Rietveld analysis)
XRF	(Trace) elements – quantitative surface analysis: SiO ₂ , Al ₂ O ₃ , K ₂ O, CaO, P ₂ O ₅ , Mg, Fe ₂ O ₃ , TiO ₂ , Na ₂ O, Zn, S, Li, Sr, MnO, Ba, B, Pb, As, Cd, Cr, Ni, Zr, Cl, Co, Cu, Rb, Y, Mo, Pt, Ti	UNI EN ISO 12677:2011 Chemical analysis of refractory products by X-ray fluorescence (XRF)

Analytical Method	Main Parameters	Relevant Standards / Literature
BET	Surface Area, Pore Size	ISO 9277:2022 Determination of the specific surface area of solids by gas adsorption - BET metho

Accurate determination of these parameters is crucial when evaluating the leaching behaviour and elemental recoverability of ash and char materials, particularly in the context of circular economy and critical raw material recovery strategies, as well as for the FactSage modelling, as planned in WP7, T7.2, of the project.

5.1.1 Proximate analysis & calorimetry

The proximate composition, including moisture, volatile matter, fixed carbon, and ash content, was determined by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) using an ELTRA THERMOSTEP analyser. The measurements were carried out under controlled heating conditions in oxidative and inert atmospheres to quantify mass losses associated with moisture evaporation, volatile matter release, and subsequent combustion of residual carbon. Each stage of mass change was automatically recorded and used to calculate the corresponding proximate parameters according to standard procedures for solid biofuels. This approach allows accurate evaluation of the fuel's composition and provides valuable insight into its thermal reactivity and decomposition behaviour, which are critical for optimizing combustion and gasification processes.

In addition, the gross calorific value (LHV) of the biomass and char samples was determined using an Automatic Isoperibol Calorimeter Parr 6400. The calorimetric measurements were performed on homogenized samples in accordance with PN-EN ISO 18125:2017 – Solid biofuels – Determination of calorific value. The results were automatically corrected for heat losses and acid formation during combustion. The obtained calorific values were further used to assess the energy potential of the studied materials and to compare the effects of pyrolysis on the energy densification of the resulting chars.

5.1.2 Elemental analyses

5.1.2.1 CHNSO

Elemental analysers are advanced devices that determine the content of carbon (C), hydrogen (H), sulphur (S), nitrogen (N), and oxygen (O) in solid samples by high-temperature combustion or pyrolysis, followed by gas separation and detection using thermal conductivity (TCD) or infrared (IR) detectors. These systems are characterized by high accuracy, reproducibility, and broad measurement ranges, making them indispensable in the characterization of fuels, biomass, polymers, and other complex materials [3]. Elemental composition was determined using two automatic analysers based on high-temperature combustion and thermal detection principles: the Eltra CHS-580 (RIC) and the FLASH 2000 CHNSO analyser (PPNT, an external laboratory).

The CHS-580 elemental analyser (ELTRA GmbH, Germany) enables simultaneous determination of carbon, hydrogen, and sulphur in solid materials. It is equipped with a resistance furnace containing a horizontal ceramic combustion tube, operating at up to 1350°C. Samples (typically 50–500 mg) are weighed into ceramic crucibles and introduced into the furnace, where they are completely oxidized in an oxygen atmosphere. The combustion gases—CO₂, H₂O, and SO₂—are passed through a dust filter, after which H₂O is chemically absorbed. The dried CO₂ and SO₂ gases are then quantitatively detected using infrared (IR) cells. This method ensures reliable results even for heterogeneous materials, making the analyser suitable for a wide range of carbonaceous samples, including coal, coke/char, and biomass [4].

The FLASH 2000 elemental analyser (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) operates based on dynamic combustion and pyrolysis techniques. In CHNS mode, samples (typically 2–4 mg) are encapsulated in tin capsules and automatically introduced into a reactor furnace operating at 900–1000°C in the presence of a defined portion of oxygen. The resulting gases are transported by Helium through a copper-filled reduction reactor, where nitrogen oxides and excess oxygen are removed. The gases then pass through a water trap and a chromatographic column, which separates CO₂, H₂O, N₂, and SO₂,

before being detected by a thermal conductivity detector (TCD). The Eager Xperience software automatically calculates concentrations and generates comprehensive analytical reports.

For oxygen analysis, the instrument operates in pyrolysis mode. Samples are weighed in silver capsules and introduced into a nickel-coated carbon reactor maintained at 1060°C under helium flow. The oxygen released from the sample reacts with carbon to form CO, which is subsequently separated chromatographically and quantified by TCD detection. This approach provides accurate oxygen determination even for complex organic matrices [5].

5.1.2.2 ICP

Elemental analyses of minor (or: trace) elements were performed using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES). The method is based on measuring the intensity of characteristic emission lines of elements excited in a high-temperature argon plasma (approximately 8,000–10,000 K). The emitted spectrum is specific to each element, enabling both qualitative and quantitative identification. As the ICP analysis can work only with liquid samples, solid samples need to be digested (dissolved) prior to the ICP analysis, using the digestion procedure suitable for the specific sample.

Analyses were carried out by different laboratories in Poland (names anonymized by abbreviations) to verify the reliability and reproducibility of the results. The following instruments were used:

- PPNT: Spectro Blue TI ICP-OES (SPECTRO Analytical Instruments)
- ETL: Agilent 5100 ICP-OES spectrometer
- IL: ICP-OES spectrometer (Thermo IRIS Intrepid)

All measurements were performed in optical emission mode, with plasma stability control and background correction applied. Each laboratory used a different digestion procedure prior to the analysis:

- PPNT: Biomass and char samples were digested in aqua regia (a mixture of HCl and HNO₃ in a 3:1 volumetric ratio) using a microwave digestion system with closed Teflon vessels. The obtained solutions were clear and free of solid residues, confirming complete digestion of the material.
- ETL: Samples were dissolved in nitric acid (HNO₃) and digested in a microwave digestion system, followed by dilution with demineralized water. The resulting solutions were clear and free from precipitates, indicating complete dissolution of the material. For each sample, two independent analytical replicates were performed to assess measurement precision.
- IL: Samples were prepared by hot digestion in *aqua regia* in a DigiPrep system. Minor traces of undissolved material remained after treatment but according to the laboratory they did not significantly affect the analytical accuracy.

As will be shown in the Results section, the three independent analyses revealed very high differences which prevented from obtaining unambiguous, fully comparable and most important, reliable reference results. Therefore, the material was subsequently sent to a fourth laboratory for additional verification and confirmation of elemental composition stability. This analysis is in progress at the moment of writing of this deliverable. In addition, it is being discussed with VTT to perform a set of digestion experiments with different digestion methods to evaluate its influence on the results of the ICP analysis.

5.1.2.3 XRF

The elemental composition of the biomass and char samples was also determined using a Bruker S1 TITAN portable energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence (EDXRF) spectrometer. The instrument is equipped with a rhodium (Rh) anode operating at up to 50 kV, 100 µA, and 4 W, and an X-Flash® Silicon Drift Detector (SDD) with an active area of 10 mm² and an energy resolution of 147 eV for the Mn K α line. Measurements were conducted using the fundamental parameter method, which enables quantification of elements without the need for reference standards.

Prior to analysis, the biomass and char samples were ground in a knife mill and dried at 105 °C until no further mass decrease was observed. The powdered material was placed in measurement cuvettes covered with a thin polypropylene film that allows unhindered transmission of X-rays, which is

particularly important for the accurate detection of light elements (Mg, Al, Si, P, S, K, Ca). The total acquisition time for a single measurement ranged from 180 to 300 seconds, and results were expressed as weight percentages.

Due to the high carbon content of the char samples, overlapping of emission spectra were observed for several light and trace elements. The carbon-rich matrix causes partial absorption of low-energy X-rays and may result in line shifts and spectral distortions, particularly for elements with similar fluorescence energies (e.g., Si, P, S). To minimize these interferences, longer measurement times and repeated analyses were employed to improve statistical accuracy.

5.1.3 Morphology, structure and other analyses

5.1.3.1 BET

The specific surface area of the biomass and char samples was determined using low-temperature nitrogen adsorption in accordance with the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) theory. This method enables the determination of the total specific surface area, pore volume, and pore size distribution of porous materials based on the relationship between the amount of adsorbed gas and the relative pressure.

Prior to analysis, the samples were degassed under vacuum at elevated temperature to remove moisture and surface contaminants that could interfere with the adsorption process. Subsequently, nitrogen adsorption–desorption isotherms were recorded and used to calculate the BET surface area, total pore volume, and the distribution of micro- and mesopores.

The BET technique is a standard method for characterizing the porous structure of solid materials, including biomass-derived products. The results provide valuable insights into surface morphology and porosity changes occurring during thermochemical conversion processes such as pyrolysis and gasification.

5.1.3.2 XRD

Phase analyses of the biomass and char samples were performed using a Bruker AXS D8 ADVANCE powder diffractometer equipped with a Cu $K\alpha$ radiation source ($\lambda = 1.5406\text{\AA}$) and a LYNXEYE XE-T detector, enabling rapid data acquisition with high energy resolution. Measurements were carried out in Bragg–Brentano ($\theta - 2\theta$) geometry using a rotating sample stage to minimize the effect of preferred orientation. The typical scanning range was $5-80^\circ 2\theta$, with a step size of $0.02^\circ 2\theta$.

The instrument operates on the patented DAVINCI design, which ensures automatic recognition and precise alignment of all optical components. The implemented TWIN/TWIN optics system allows fast switching between focusing (Bragg–Brentano) and parallel-beam geometries, enabling optimal adjustment of measurement conditions to the material characteristics. The detector provides selective filtering of background and fluorescence radiation, resulting in a high signal-to-background ratio and improved detection of minor phases.

The XRD technique allows for a non-destructive determination of the phase composition and degree of crystallinity of biomass samples and their thermochemical conversion products, as well as for the identification of structural transformations occurring during thermal processes.

5.2 Analytical results

5.2.1 Proximate analysis & calorimetry

The results of thermogravimetric analysis and calorimetry are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. The results of thermogravimetric analysis and calorimetry. Abbreviations: VM – volatile matter, FC – fixed carbon, LHV – lower heating value. All values reported on “as received” basis.

Feedstock	Moisture [%-wt]	Ash [%-wt]	VM [%-wt]	FC [%-wt]	LHV [MJ/kg]
MMX	5.19±0.20	2.72±0.24	75.9±1.3	16.2±1.1	16.9±0.4
CW	6.08±0.18	0.245±0.065	76.7±0.7	16.9±0.7	18.1±0.3
HAY	7.58±0.01	8.83±0.21	69.0±1.5	14.6±1.5	15.0±0.4
DW	13.2±0.1	0.385±0.039	71.8±1.1	14.6±1.1	16.9±0.3
SGR	6.19±0.14	5.11±0.35	73.4±0.6	15.3±0.9	17.2±0.1
MMX Char	0.713±0.119	9.20±0.11	10.5±1.1	79.6±1.0	30.5±0.1
CW Char	0.89±0.03	1.09±0.12	12.8±0.9	85.3±0.9	33.3±0.3
HAY Char	3.39±0.04	26.2±0.2	17.2±1.1	53.3±1.2	22.1±0.2
DW Char	2.48±0.11	2.31±0.21	14.9±1.1	80.3±1.0	32.6±0.2
SGR Char	0.392±0.080	19.2±0.5	10.6±1.3	69.9±1.2	28.1±0.1

The results of thermogravimetric analysis and calorimetric measurements clearly differentiate the studied biomasses and their corresponding chars in terms of fuel quality and thermal behaviour. Among the raw materials, CW demonstrated the most advantageous characteristics, with exceptionally low ash content (<0.3%), which is typical for wood-based feedstocks, as well as the highest volatile matter fraction (~77%) and calorific value (18.1 MJ/kg). MMX also showed favourable fuel properties, characterized by low moisture and moderate ash levels, while maintaining a comparable energy value (16.9 MJ/kg). In contrast, HAY exhibited significantly higher ash content (8.8%) and a reduced calorific value (15.0 MJ/kg), consistent with nutrient-rich agricultural residues. Similarly, SGR, being a herbaceous biomass, presented a moderate ash accumulation (5.11%) but maintained a relatively high calorific value (17.2 MJ/kg). Despite being a renewable and sustainable energy resource, due to their high ash content and ash composition (see Section 5.2.1.2) these types of biomass are prone to cause slagging and fouling during combustion and gasification, which requires the application of special operating conditions and/or countermeasures to achieve stable operation of the gasifier or furnace. DW, despite their slightly higher moisture content (13.2%), presented relatively low ash (0.39%) and a moderate calorific value (16.9 MJ/kg), indicating high potential for energy recovery.

Pyrolysis markedly altered the composition and energy characteristics of the materials. All chars exhibited a substantial increase in fixed carbon (up to 85%) and a twofold rise in calorific value compared to the raw biomass, reaching 33.3 MJ/kg for CW Char and 30.5 MJ/kg for MMX Char. These results confirm efficient volatile release and strong carbon densification during thermal conversion. CW Char, with its very low ash content (1.1%) and the highest heating value, stands out as the most suitable material for high-energy or sorbent applications, in the case that the recovery of specific elements would turn out not to be feasible or profitable. Conversely, HAY Char became ash-dominated (26%), indicating high potential suitability for nutrient or mineral recovery. SGR Char followed a comparable trend of significant mineral densification, reaching an ash content of 19.2%, though it preserved a solid energetic value with an LHV of 28.1 MJ/kg. DW Char, with the ash content comparable to CW also showed a similarly high LHV, being 32.6 MJ/kg.

5.2.1.1 CHNSO

Table 4 presents the results obtained during the elemental analysis. The analyses of carbon (C), hydrogen (H), and sulphur (S) were performed at the Biomass and Waste Valorisation Laboratory at RIC

using a CHS analyser, while the determination of nitrogen (N) and oxygen (O) contents was outsourced to PPNT to ensure full compositional coverage.

For raw biomass the values for C, H, and S remain in ranges typical for biomass materials. Nitrogen (N) is reported below the detection limit, which is unusual for biomass samples when comparing to other characterization results, where the reported nitrogen content in Miscanthus was between 0.13 and 0.33% [6] and even 0.67% [7]. Furthermore, for the clean wood nitrogen content of 0.2% was reported [6]. Due to this issue nitrogen was not measured for HAY, DW, SGR and their chars.

Table 4. The results of elemental analyses CHNSO. All values on “as received” basis.

Feedstock	C [%-wt]	H [%-wt]	N [%-wt]	S [%-wt]	O [%-wt]
MMX	50.1±0.2	4.66±0.07	<LOD	0.0432±0.0041	31.65
CW	53.8±0.6	4.88±0.12	<LOD	0.00752±0.00062	31.72
HAY	45.6±0.6	4.64±0.10	n.m.	0.177±0.024	n.m.
DW	51.0±3.4	5.07±0.32	n.m.	0.0182±0.0042	n.m.
SGR	48.1±0.7	4.34±0.04	n.m.	0.0272±0.0026	n.m.
MMX Char	90.9±0.4	1.99±0.01	<LOD	0.108±0.005	10.38
CW Char	98.7±0.4	2.28±0.04	<LOD	0.00336±0.00100	10.311
HAY Char	67.1±0.6	1.70±0.02	n.m.	0.225±0.007	n.m.
DW Char	96.3±0.3	2.44±0.07	n.m.	0.055±0.007	n.m.
SGR Char	82.3±0.5	1.74±0.02	n.m.	0.0460±0.0027	n.m.

After pyrolysis, all char samples exhibited a substantial increase in carbon content, exceeding 90% for MMX, CW, and DW chars, with a simultaneous drop in hydrogen to around 2%. This clearly indicates efficient devolatilization and the formation of a highly carbonized matrix. The corresponding reduction in oxygen content to approximately 10% confirms the removal of oxygen-containing functional groups from the biomass structure. As a result, the char becomes more carbon-rich and thermally stable, with a structure that is less reactive. Among the tested materials, CW Char reached the highest carbon content (98.7%) and the lowest sulphur content (0.003%).

In contrast, the herbaceous biomasses (HAY and SGR) exhibited different elemental profiles compared to the woody feedstocks and Miscanthus. HAY and HAY Char contained the highest amounts of sulphur (0.18–0.23%) and lower carbon concentrations (reaching only 67.1% for the char), consistent with the higher mineral content of herbaceous biomass. SGR Char achieved a carbon content of 82.3% while maintaining a relatively low sulphur level (0.046%). The elemental trends observed for demolition wood (DW and DW Char) similarly reflect progressive carbon enrichment during pyrolysis, although the slightly higher variability in hydrogen and sulphur may indicate heterogeneity typical of waste-derived materials.

The CHNSO data confirm that the pyrolysis process leads to strong carbon concentration and deoxygenation across all samples. The very high carbon content observed in these chars may, however, limit the leachability of inorganic elements, as the dense carbon matrix can physically encapsulate mineral phases and reduce their accessibility to the leaching medium.

5.2.1.2 ICP

To verify the reliability of the elemental composition results, the set of biomass and char samples were analysed independently in three different external analytical laboratories (ETL, IL, and PPNT) using the ICP-OES technique. The obtained results are presented in Table 5, Table 6 and Table 7. The overall compositional trend, especially the presence and amounts of the elements like K, P, Ca, and Si was consistent with expectations related to the individual biomass types; however, certain significant discrepancies were observed, likely resulting from incomplete digestion, matrix interferences, or

instrumental and calibration limitations. Not all biomass and char samples were analysed at each external laboratory.

Looking at the datasets provided by PPNT and IL, the IL dataset shows a similar overall pattern but with significantly lower absolute concentration values for most macroelements (K, Ca, Mg, P) and better detection of trace metals such as Fe, Mn, Cr, and Pb. For the macroelements the differences were even as high as an order of the magnitude, e.g. K concentration in the MMX char amounts 22.5 mg/g (PPNT), 0.181 mg/g (IL), while in the CW char these values are respectively 2.34 mg/g (PPNT) and 0.145 mg/g (IL). The third laboratory, ETL reports 14.8 mg/g and 1.555 mg/g for MMX char and CW char, respectively. It is clear that the differences are very large and cannot be attributed solely to the heterogeneity of the samples, which actually were homogenized and mixed before preparing sample for the analyses.

A further comparative analysis of the three datasets demonstrates systematic differences in the absolute concentrations of major and trace elements. Although the overall trends remain consistent (i.e., enrichment of inorganic species in char samples relative to their parent biomasses), the magnitude of these enrichments vary considerably between laboratories.

The discrepancies mainly arise from:

- Differences in digestion chemistry and completeness. *Aqua regia* (used by PPNT and IL) dissolves silicates less efficiently than nitric acid (used by ETL), but it more effectively releases metals bound to organic matrices.
- Sample heterogeneity and non-uniform mineral distribution. The carbon-rich, porous structure of the chars to irregular dispersion of particles, resulting in limited representativeness of subsamples.
- Matrix effects of plasma. High carbon content and residual solids can alter aerosol transport and excitation efficiency, reducing signal intensity for light elements (e.g., Si, Al, Mg).
- Instrumental factors. Different spectrometers, emission line selections, and background corrections caused systematic deviations, particularly for K, Ca, and P.

These factors collectively explain the limited repeatability and reproducibility observed across laboratories. Despite the use of standardized conditions, the high heterogeneity and complex carbonaceous matrix of the chars made it challenging to obtain consistent quantitative data. In addition, the applied digestion procedures and their varying efficiency had a significant impact on the obtained results, as incomplete or uneven mineralization could lead to underestimation of certain elements, particularly those bound within silicate or refractory phases. Therefore, the samples were submitted to a fourth independent laboratory for additional verification and confirmation of elemental results.

Table 5. Concentrations of inorganic (trace) elements in biomass and char samples determined by ICP-OES – PPNT laboratory (mg/g dry basis).

Element	MMX	CW	SGR	MMX Char	CW Char
Si	22.5	0.150	0.1156	43.9	0.751
Al	0.286	0.178	0.5159	0.703	0.483
K	5.59	0.211	0.7295	22.5	2.34
Ca	4.39	1.74	1.1131	14.4	8.47
P	1.30	<LOD	0.0909	3.91	1.04
Mg	0.581	0.222	0.4689	2.06	1.04
Fe	0.333	0.159	0.0816	0.832	0.0711
Ti	0.0138	<LOD	n.m.	0.129	<LOD
Na	0.220	0.435	0.5457	1.66	1.45
Zn	0.374	0.0127	0.0140	0.753	0
S	1.72	0.275	0.1955	3.91	0.312
Li	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Sr	0.0107	<LOD	0.0052	<LOD	<LOD
Mn	0.0248	0.0761	0.0151	0.103	0.367
Ba	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	<LOD	0.310
B	<LOD	0.0745	0.0156	0.347	0.212
Pb	0.0194	<LOD	0.0048	0.147	0.0906
As	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Cd	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Cr	<LOD	0.0234	n.m.	0.535	0.139
Ni	0.184	0.0244	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Zr	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Co	<LOD	0.0239	n.m.	<LOD	0.0711
Se	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	<LOD	0.0627
Bi	<LOD	0.0178	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Cu	n.m.	n.m.	0.0789	n.m.	n.m.
Mo	0.0119	<LOD	n.m.	<LOD	<LOD
Hg	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Sb	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Sn	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
V	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.

Table 6. Concentrations of inorganic (trace) elements in biomass and char samples determined by ICP-OES – IL laboratory (mg/g dry basis). Note: blank column means that the sample was not analysed.

Element	HAY	DW	MMX Char	CW Char	HAY Char	DW Char
Si	19.3	5.43	31.6	9.56	32.1	10.8
Al	0.608	0.0255	0.115	0.0437	3.46	0.0884
K	2.65	0.107	1.81	0.145	4.78	0.156
Ca	1.73	0.567	1.17	0.502	2.44	0.671
P	0.102	0.00139	0.0459	0.00347	0.222	0.00141
Mg	0.576	0.125	0.295	0.0941	0.916	0.0781
Fe	0.860	0.450	0.304	0.0534	2.06	0.749
Ti	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Na	4.90	0.634	2.20	0.514	8.91	0.828
Zn	0.0175	0.0254	0.264	0.00541	0.0376	0.0673
S	0.958	0.136	0.193	0.0322	1.06	0.218
Li	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Sr	0.0160	0.00241	0.0141	0.00148	0.0483	0.00303
Mn	0.169	0.101	0.0449	0.0459	0.366	0.0553
Ba	0.0125	0.00365	0.0379	0.0163	0.0398	0.00893
B	0.0105	0.00442	0.00566	0.00267	0.0328	0.00341
Pb	0.00160	0.00198	0.0155	0.00143	0.0048	0.00275
As	0.00090	0.00058	0.00132	0.00098	<LOD	0.00105
Cd	0.00045	0.00032	0.00043	<LOD	0.00107	0.00022
Cr	0.00657	0.00079	0.0221	0.00056	0.0180	0.00123
Ni	0.00020	<LOD	<LOD	0.00419	0.00158	<LOD
Zr	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Co	0.00011	0.00701	<LOD	0.00013	0.00046	0.00464
Se	0.00219	0.00064	<LOD	<LOD	0.00035	<LOD
Bi	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Cu	0.00605	0.00225	0.00282	0.00075	0.0132	0.0108
Mo	0.00071	<LOD	0.00026	<LOD	0.00155	<LOD
Hg	0.00019	0.00020	0.00021	0.00020	0.00020	0.00021
Sb	<LOD	0.00025	0.00062	0.00047	<LOD	0.00023
Sn	0.00412	0.00387	0.00488	0.00505	0.00523	0.00481
V	0.00251	0.00222	0.00175	0.00205	0.00699	0.00209

Table 7. Concentrations of inorganic (trace) elements in biomass and char samples determined by ICP-OES – ETL laboratory (mg/g dry basis).

Element	MMX Char	CW Char	HAY Char	DW Char	SGR Char
Si	14.7	0.499	16.6	1.086	5.4
Al	0.161	0.096	5.01	0.214	0.227
K	14.8	1.555	43.8	0.782	4.2
Ca	6.864	2.583	24.4	4.22	11.7
P	1.75	0.202	8.127	0.136	4.8
Mg	1.16	0.591	6.094	0.645	3.9
Fe	0.378	0.065	3.9	2.457	0.249
Ti	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Na	0.074	0.111	1.805	0.184	0.393
Zn	0.448	<LOD	0.08	0.12	<LOD
S	0.73	0.091	1.346	0.404	0.606
Li	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	n.m.
Sr	<LOD	<LOD	0.038	<LOD	<LOD
Mn	0.054	0.218	0.369	0.255	0.037
Ba	0.057	0.031	0.055	0.028	<LOD
B	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0.032
Pb	0.039	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
As	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Cd	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Cr	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Ni	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Zr	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Co	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	0.039	<LOD
Se	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	<LOD
Bi	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Cu	<LOD	<LOD	0.021	0.04	<LOD
Mo	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Hg	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Sb	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
Sn	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.	n.m.
V	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD

5.2.1.3 XRF

The XRF analysis provided preliminary information on the elemental composition of the investigated biomass and char samples (Table 8). The results revealed clear differences between the feedstocks, with MMX showing considerably higher contents of SiO₂ (22.4 mg/g), K₂O (8.63 mg/g), CaO (4.26 mg/g), and Cl (7.33 mg/g) compared to CW, which contained only minor amounts of these oxides. This trend reflects the naturally higher mineral content and ash-forming tendency of herbaceous biomass, in contrast to the low inorganic content characteristic of woody materials.

After pyrolysis, both chars exhibited a pronounced enrichment in inorganic constituents, resulting from the loss of volatile matter and the concentration of non-volatile mineral species. For example, in MMX Char, the contents of SiO₂, K₂O, and CaO increased more than two times compared to the raw biomass, reaching 54.4, 37.2, and 15.2 mg/g, respectively. CW Char also showed an increase in CaO (11.4 mg/g) and an enrichment in K₂O (2.61 mg/g). However, Cl concentrations remained nearly unchanged both in the feedstocks and in the chars (5.99–7.77 mg/g), indicating partial volatilization of chlorine compounds during pyrolysis, which is usually observed in this kind of processes [8].

Table 8. Concentration of elements in biomass and corresponding char samples determined by XRF (mg/g dry basis). Oxide values were converted to elemental concentrations, where appropriate.

Compound	MMX	CW	MMX Char	CW Char
SiO ₂	22.4	<LOD	54.4	<LOD
Al ₂ O ₃	<LOD	<LOD	7.23	<LOD
K ₂ O	8.63	0.257	37.2	2.61
CaO	4.26	1.97	15.2	11.4
P ₂ O ₅	<LOD	<LOD	4.05	<LOD
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.420	<LOD	1.24	<LOD
TiO ₂	<LOD	<LOD	0.138	<LOD
Zn	0.66	<LOD	2.04	0.110
S	2.14	<LOD	3.47	<LOD
Sr	<LOD	<LOD	0.08	<LOD
MnO	<LOD	0.209	0.155	1.05
Cl	7.33	6.01	7.77	5.99
Cu	<LOD	0.0700	<LOD	0.040
Pt	0.100	<LOD	0.360	<LOD

However, when considering the results of the XRF analysis it has to be taken into the account, that this analytical method is a non-destructive, surface-scanning technique. Therefore, for the non-homogeneous, carbon-rich matrix like the biomass and char particles the repeatability of the XRF measurements is limited. The inhomogeneity of the powdered samples caused signal variability and spectral overlaps, which affected the precision of the measurements. For this reason, after analysing two biomass and two char samples it was decided to discontinue the use of XRF for quantitative elemental analysis. Instead, the determination of inorganic elements was subsequently performed using ICP-OES, where better accuracy and repeatability is expected, due to the fact that the sample is dissolved, and hence also the subsurface elements will be reflected in the results, at least as long as the digestion procedure is performed properly.

5.2.2 Morphology, structure and other analyses

5.2.2.1 BET

The BET analysis (Table 9) revealed a substantial increase in specific surface area and a decrease in pore size after pyrolysis for both feedstocks. The raw MMX and CW exhibited very low surface areas (0.723 and 0.952 m²/g, respectively) and large average pore diameters (>50 Å), typical for compact, non-porous biomass structures.

After conversion to char, most samples showed a huge rise in surface area — up to 317.7 m²/g for MMX char and 418.1 m²/g for CW char — accompanied by a reduction in pore size to approximately 17 Å. Similar effective pore development was observed for DW and SGR chars, which achieved high specific surface areas of 374.3 m²/g and 368.3 m²/g, with average pore sizes of 12.50 Å and 18.30 Å, respectively. This indicates the formation of a fine microporous structure during pyrolysis, as volatile compounds are released, the particle structure and carbon matrix become more developed and expanded [9].

In contrast, the HAY char exhibited significantly different textural properties, achieving a very low surface area of only 10.4 m²/g and a small pore size of 10.68 Å. This suggests limited pore network expansion or pore blockage during carbonization, which may be attributed to its specific chemical composition, such as a higher ash content at pyrolysis temperatures.

Table 9. BET surface area and pore size of feedstock and char samples.

Feedstock	BET Surface Area [m ² /g]	Pore Size [Å]
MMX	0.723	75.15
CW	0.952	52.05
MMX Char	317.7	17.29
CW Char	418.1	17.25
HAY Char	10.4	10.68
DW Char	374.3	12.50
SGR Char	368.3	18.3

Overall, the CW char demonstrates slightly higher surface area and smaller pores compared to MMX char, suggesting more effective pore development during carbonization. It was also decided not to perform BET analyses on the samples of the remaining raw biomass types (HAY, DW, SGR). This is because of the expected low surface area, as already seen from the results of CW and MMX, but more importantly due to the lower importance for the future work related to the recovery of elements.

5.2.2.2 XRD

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the biomass samples (MMX and CW) and their corresponding chars exhibited a dominant amorphous character, preventing phase identification due to the absence of identifiable crystalline reflections.

For the biomass samples (**Figure 16**, **Figure 17**), broad scattering bands typical for lignocellulosic structures were observed around 15–17°, 22–23°, and 34–35° 2 θ , indicating the predominance of disordered cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. In the char samples (**Figure 18**, **Figure 19**), the cellulose peaks disappeared, and a broad graphite-like feature (~24–26° 2 θ) appeared, with a weaker shoulder near 42–44° 2 θ , characteristic of low-crystallinity turbostratic carbon [10].

Figure 16. XRD spectrum of raw MMX.

Figure 17. XRD spectrum of MMX Char.

Figure 18. XRD spectrum of raw CW.

Figure 19. XRD spectrum of CW char.

Due to the heterogeneous nature of the samples and the dominance of the signal by the amorphous carbon forms, signal reproducibility was limited, reflected by higher standard deviation values. As shown in the figures above, it was not possible to identify any peaks specific to any crystalline compounds, which would be of significant added value, amending the elemental analysis results presented in earlier sections. Rietveld refinement was not applicable, and the analysis was restricted to qualitative assessment of amorphous structure. Therefore, due to a limited added value for further research, it was decided to discontinue further XRD analyses.

5.3 Discussion

In the previous paragraphs a set of results from different analytical methods applied to the selected biomass types and their chars was presented. The following observations can be made:

- The results of the proximate analysis of raw biomass samples are in agreement with the ranges given in other data sources. In the context of the BeBOP project, the moisture content of all biomasses is well suitable for the gasification process. Woody fuels contain low amounts of ash, with DW having ca. 50% more ash than CW, which is expected, and can be attributed to the presence of e.g. paints, wood impregnations, or foreign inorganic matter deposited onto the wood surface. Herbaceous biomass has a much higher ash content, with HAY having the top value of nearly 9%-wt.
- The proximate analysis of the char samples confirms the release of volatiles during the pyrolysis process. Due to the release of the moisture and volatile matter, other constituents appear more concentrated, e.g. HAY ash reaching 26%-wt. and MMX nearly 10%-wt.
- The calorific values of the raw biomass samples are also in agreement with the values found in other data sources. Char has the LHV similar to coal, with HAY being an exception, due to the high ash content, which comes at the cost of the carbon content. This is also clearly visible in the elemental CHNSO results.
- BET results are mainly important for the leaching experiments. From the results it is clear that char is much more porous than the raw biomass, and that there are also differences among the chars from different types of biomass. This parameter will be taken into the account when comparing the leaching efficiencies between different types of char.
- Similarly, the XRF results may be helpful during the assessment of the leaching results. As the XRF is a surface measurement it may help in explaining the differences in leaching efficiencies by comparing the XRF results to ICP results, with ICP theoretically measuring the total amount of an element in the sample. A higher leaching efficiency could be expected when higher fraction of an element is measured on the char surface, compared to the situation where this fraction is lower. There is a caveat, however. The deposition of the elements on the char surface can be very inhomogeneous, which can lead to large differences between the analysed samples

of the same material. Considering the fact that the XRF results are based on a single analysis, this could lead to misleading conclusions and this fact has to be taken into the account when comparing the XRF data with e.g. the ICP results.

- From the perspective of FactSage simulations more than the elemental composition the structural composition is needed. Unfortunately, the XRD analyses did not provide any useful information about the (crystalline) species present in the char due to the heavy noise from the bulk carbon, as explained earlier.

The amount and the chemical composition of the ash can be evaluated from different perspectives. From the perspective of the gasification process and the gasification experiments in the pilot scale, which will be performed during the implementation of WP3 of the BeBOP, CW and DW are the most suitable as basic or reference fuels. Woody fuels are commonly known as being least problematic for the gasifier operation, due to their low ash content, low amount of alkali metals and chlorine in the ash and therefore a minimal chance of the occurrence of ash sintering and bed agglomeration during the operation. Ash- and alkali-rich fuels are on the opposite side, as due to their ash properties, and especially a much lower ash melting point they are known to cause operational problems, not only due to the agglomeration and sintering of the bed material in fluidized bed reactors, but also due to the increased fouling of the downstream units of operation, putting higher burden on the gas cleaning units, especially the filters. In short, gasifier operation with ash-rich fuels is possible, but more challenging. Nonetheless this kind of fuels are very relevant from the sustainability point of view, and in addition can be cultivated on marginal lands where no food crops can be cultivated, often also acting as a “natural soil purifier” by means of phytoremediation.

From the perspective of the research on the recovery of valuable elements, which is being implemented in WP7 and WP8 of the BeBOP project, MMX, HAY and SGR are the most interesting. This is exactly due to the same reason as why these types of biomass are troublesome for the gasification process, namely their ash content and composition. In the case of MMX, the fact of being grown on marginal polluted lands, lead to an observable increase of the content of metals like Zn and Pb in the ash, making them possibly attractive as a renewable source of these, and possibly other metals. SGR was also grown on contaminated land, but here the analysis of the trace elements did not reveal increased concentrations of heavy metals. This could be due to the difference in which Miscanthus and Switchgrass accumulate heavy metals in their plant structure, but this aspect falls outside the scope of the research in this project. Furthermore, high shares of K, P, Ca and Mg make them a potentially interesting substrate for the recovery of elements or compounds needed for the production of fertilizers. Phosphorus (P) is included in the European list of the Critical Raw Materials (CRM).

From the abovementioned perspective of the work on the recovery of valuable elements from gasification residues the information about the content of trace (inorganic) elements in the char is critical and should be provided mainly by the results of the ICP analysis. In this context important observations were made, namely that the results from the analysis of the same substrate differ strongly and depend on the laboratory where the substrate was analysed. Upon inquiry it was discovered that despite the fact that each laboratory is informed about the nature of the sample (here: biomass char), they used different digestion methods, which probably lead to large differences in the results, sometimes even up to an order of the magnitude. The comparison of the ICP results for each type of biomass char is presented in Figure 20 to Figure 23. Noticeable are the differences between the concentrations of e.g. K, Ca, P, S and Si – all these elements are very relevant from the leaching experiments point of view. Besides, it will not be possible to reliably calculate and compare the leaching or recovery efficiencies, if the composition of the reference material is not accurately quantified. Therefore, additional investigations of this matter have been initiated, including additional characterization with the use of a given digestion method. A literature review revealed that microwave-assisted nitric acid digestion is more suitable for char than *aqua regia* digestion [11] [12] [13]. At the moment of writing char samples are being analysed at two more laboratories and the results will be added to this deliverable as soon as they become available.

Figure 20. ICP-OES results for the 17 most abundant elements in MMX char provided by three different laboratories. Noticeable are the differences between the concentrations of e.g. K, Ca, P, S and Si – all very relevant from the leaching experiments point of view.

Figure 21. ICP-OES results for the 17 most abundant elements in CW char provided by three different laboratories. Noticeable are the differences between the concentrations of e.g. K, Ca, P, S and Si – all very relevant from the leaching experiments point of view. Two samples analysed by the same laboratory (IL01 and IL02), however, show similar results, except for Si.

Figure 22. ICP-OES results for the 17 most abundant elements in HAY char provided by two different laboratories. Noticeable are the differences between the concentrations of e.g. K, Ca, P, and Mg – all very relevant from the leaching experiments point of view.

Figure 23. ICP-OES results for the 17 most abundant elements in DW char provided by three different laboratories. Noticeable are the differences between the concentrations of e.g. K, Ca, Mg, Fe and Si – all very relevant from the leaching experiments point of view.

6. Conclusions

In this deliverable the results of the characterization of biomass and char samples were described. Clean wood (CW), Recovery / post-consumer/ demolition wood (DW), a blend of Miscanthus genotypes (MMX), Hay (HAY) and Switchgrass (SGR) were the types of biomass ultimately selected for characterization.

Biomass samples were partially obtained from commercial suppliers (CW, HAY), DW was collected and pre-processed (chipped) in-house, while MMX and SGR were cultivated on marginal contaminated land in Poland and Greece, respectively as a part of former European research projects [MISCOMAR](#) (Facce Surplus 1st call) and [GOLD](#) (Horizon 2020, GA 101006873).

Proximate and ultimate composition of each biomass type and its char was carried out, as well as characterization of morphology and structure. Analytical techniques involved were thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) for moisture, ash, volatile matter and fixed carbon content, analysis of major elements (CHSNO), analysis of minor (or trace) elements (ICP-OES, XRF), analysis of crystalline structure (XRD), determination of the porosity and surface area (BET), and bomb calorimetry for the determination of the calorific value.

In general, the obtained results were in line with the results obtained for similar types of biomass found in the literature. All raw samples were relatively dry (moisture content <13%-wt). Woody biomass (CW, DW) had the lowest ash content (values below 0.5%-wt), while MMX, SGR and HAY showed significantly higher values, with HAY peaking at 8.83%-wt. From the gasification experiments in the pilot scale (WP3 of the BeBOP project) point of view CW and DW are the most suitable as basic or reference fuels due to the least problematic gasifier operation (minimal chance of ash sintering and bed agglomeration). However, from the research on the recovery of valuable elements (WP7 and WP8) perspective, MMX, HAY and likely SGR are the most interesting, due to their relatively high content of inorganics and, in the case of MMX, the fact of being grown on marginal polluted lands, which lead to the increased content of metals like Zn and Pb in the ash.

During the analysis of the results an important observation was made, namely the difference between the results from the ICP analyses performed on the same substrates, but in different laboratories. These differences cannot be attributed solely to the inhomogeneous nature of the sample. It was concluded, that the differences were mainly caused by the application of different digestion methods, and that this led to a large spread of the measured concentrations, sometimes the differences for the same element were reached even an order of a magnitude. From the perspective of the assessment of the recovery efficiency and the elemental mass balance closure this is not acceptable. Therefore, additional analyses are planned to identify the most appropriate digestion procedure to be used in the future analysis of trace elements in the char, taking away the uncertainty about the composition of the char, which is of key importance for the assessment of the recovery/leaching strategies that are being investigated in the BeBOP project.

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